

ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ACUPRESSURE IN NAUSEA AND VOMITING IN PREGNANCY

Zufarov Pulat Saatovich

professor of the Department of Clinical Pharmacology, Tashkent
medical academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Aripjanova Shahlo Sardarovna

assistant of the Department of Clinical Pharmacology, Tashkent medical
academy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Tursunova Zebunniso Avazbek qizi

5th year student of treatment faculty №1, Tashkent medical academy,
Tashkent

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Abstract

Most of the pregnant women experience nausea and vomiting during pregnancy. Of this, 3-5% of cases are accompanied by severe nausea and vomiting in women. Nausea and vomiting in 34% of women begin in the first 4 weeks, while in an 8-week period 85% percent women experience morning sickness. Although there are many of the antiemetic drugs in pregnancy, it is still important to find and introduce nonmedicamentous, safe methods for the treatment of nausea and vomiting of pregnant women. In this research, seabands which based on accupressure method, used in nausea and vomiting during pregnancy and effectivness is assessed. All sea bands were prepared in home condition. Results were assessed according to PUQE-24 scale. Accupressure method was helpful to relieve nausea and vomiting in mild and moderate symptoms.

Key words: Accupressura, morning sickness, sea bands

Relevance. Almost 85% of pregnant women experience nausea and vomiting during pregnancy. Of this, 3-5% of cases are accompanied by severe nausea and vomiting in women. Nausea and vomiting in 34% of women begin in the first 4 weeks, while in an 8-week period 85% percent women experience morning sickness(1). About 30 % of women experiencing morning sickness are treated in a hospital. (2)Also due to hyperemesis gravidarum, about 10% of women are forced to terminate the pregnancy. Currently, medicamentous drugs have been widely used in the treatment of vomiting and nausea. Even so, there is a lot of controversial debate about the safety and effectiveness of the drug substances used in pregnancy. That is why it is now important to develop nonmedicamentous, safe methods for the treatment of nausea and vomiting of pregnant women. There is information in foreign literature that the acupressure method reduces the symptoms of morning sickness, this method is included in Group B. To determine the degree of prevalence of this method in our republic, we conducted a survey of pregnant women. It shows the results of 400 surveys in the following diagrams.

Chart 1

When asked if you had toxicosis in pregnancy, 78% of pregnant women answered yes. The question of which symptoms are most annoying in morning sickness is answered as nausea (44 %), vomiting (31 %), retching (25%). When asked if you used acupressure seabands in pregnancy, 97% of women answered “ No, because I haven't heard about it,” while 1% of women answered Yes, 2% of women answered “ No, because I don't believe in effectiveness.” Also, considering that these seabands are not sold on the territory of Uzbekistan, seabands were prepared at home condition, and were tested on pregnant women.

Purpose of the experiment: To study the effectiveness of special seabands based on the acupressure method in the treatment of nausea and vomiting.

Objects and techniques: The experiment was carried out in the 88th family polyclinic of the Yangihayot district. 30 pregnant women were involved for the experiment. The duration of pregnancy in women was on average 8.5 weeks (or 6-11 weeks). The age of pregnant women was on average 23 years (20-25 years). Women with mild to moderate levels of nausea and vomiting were involved in the experiment. Women with severe toxicosis, with a risk of pregnancy complications, as well as chronic diseases – hypertension, bronchial asthma, diabetes mellitus-were not involved in the experiment.

Chart 2

Statistical characteristic of pregnant women

Women were divided into two groups by random selection. Group 1 was the examining group and they were given bracelets with a special button that pressed the P6 point (2 cm above the paw wrist joint). Group 2 was a control group, and bracelets were distributed to them, which did not have a pressing button. Women in both groups were not limited to taking vitamin Compounds (Elevit prenatal), folic acid, iodine preparations, hafitol. Women wore seabands for 7 days when symptoms of morning sickness were manifested. The results were evaluated on the PUQE-24 scale according to the total time of nausea within 24 hours, the number of vomiting and the retching

PUQE-24 form

On average in a day for how long you feel nauseated or sick to your stomach				
>6 hour 5 points	4-6 hour 4 points	2-3 hour 3 points	< 1 hour 2 points	Not at all 1 points

On average in a day, how many times do you vomit or throw up?				
more than 7 5 points	5-6 times 4 points	3-4 times 3 points	1-2 times 2 points	Not at all 1 points

On average in a day, how many times have you had retching or dry heaves without bringing anything up?				
more than 7 5 points	5-6 times 4 points	3-4 times 3 points	1-2 times 2 points	Not at all 1 points

Results and discussion. The natures of the PUQE-24 scale in the examination group for 7 days are demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1

	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day7
Treatment group	9	8,33	7,8	7,3	6,6	6,1	5,5
Control group	9,8	9,5	9	8,8	8,6	8	7,8

The PUQE -24 index changed from 9 (moderate) to 5.5 (mild level)in the treatment group. In the control group, it changed from 9.8 (moderate)to 7.8 (moderate).

Conclusion In mild and moderate nausea and vomiting in pregnancies, seabands based on point P6 acupressure are effective. It also observed that, it especially reduces nausea in morning sickness. Taking into account the fact that these seabands are not produced and sold on the territory of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to establish its production or prepare it at home conditions.

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